

STORAGE REQUIREMENTS AND SHELF LIFE OF THE DIURETIC HERBAL PREPARATION 'ALERVA'

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Relevance. Herbal preparations are medicinal products based on plant components such as herbs, flowers, roots, and fruits. They possess various therapeutic and restorative properties and are often used as preventive remedies. It is important to remember that proper storage of herbal preparations and adherence to their expiration dates directly affect their effectiveness and safety.

The shelf life of herbal preparations directly depends on their composition, method of preparation, and packaging form. Manufacturers usually indicate a shelf life of 1 to 3 years on the packaging of herbal products. It is important to follow the recommended storage conditions and periods, as herbal preparations may lose their medicinal properties after the expiration date.

Following storage recommendations and using the products in a timely manner ensures the preservation of the beneficial properties of herbal preparations and maximizes their health benefits.

Objective. The aim of our research is to analyze the storage conditions and shelf life of the diuretic herbal preparation "Alerva," developed at the Department of Pharmacognosy and Standardization of Medicinal Products.

Materials and Methods. Experiments to determine the storage conditions of the filter-bag preparation "Alerva" were conducted to assess quality indicators of the finished product: appearance, authenticity, moisture content (%), degree of grinding (mm), mass of one package (g), content of water-soluble extractive substances (%), microbiological purity, and total flavonoid content (measured as rutin, %) under natural conditions — stored for 30 months in a room at 25 ± 2.0 °C and relative humidity of 60–75%. These parameters were compared with the initial quality indicators.

The herbal preparation "Alerva" in filter-bag form was packed in containers approved for medical use. Storage of the filter-bag preparation "Alerva" under natural conditions was monitored over 2.5 years by evaluating quality indicators every 6 months and determining the content of active substances.

Results. The study results showed that the diuretic herbal preparation "Alerva," packaged in three different types of packaging materials, maintained its qualitative and quantitative characteristics throughout the 30-month observation period. However, the quality indicators of the herbal mixture packed in aluminum foil and nylon bags were lower than those of the mixture packed in filter paper bags. Therefore, the priority of packaging materials was as follows: filter paper bag > aluminum foil bag > nylon bag.

Conclusions. The diuretic herbal preparation "Alerva" stored under natural conditions for 30 months was evaluated according to the studied quality parameters and technical requirements. It was established that the most optimal packaging for "Alerva" is a filter paper bag. Additionally, the shelf life of the preparation under room temperature (25 ± 2.0 °C) and relative humidity not exceeding 75% was determined to be 2 years.